

NeXus and NOMAD: Research Data Management Workflows for Standardised Multidimensional Characterization Techniques

Sandor Brockhauser¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6403-9022>

¹ Department of Physics and CSMB, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Berlin, Germany

² Department of Heterogeneous Reactions, Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion, Stiftstr. 34-36, 45470 Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany

³ Leibniz-Institut für Kristallzüchtung (IKZ), Max-Born-Straße 2, 12489 Berlin, Germany

⁴ ITMC-Institute for Technical and Macromolecular Chemistry, RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany

⁵ DWI–Leibniz Institute for Interactive Materials e.V., Aachen, Germany

⁶ Fritz Haber Institute of the Max Planck Society, Faradayweg 4-6, 14195 Berlin, Germany

⁷ Physics Department, RPTU Kaiserslautern-Landau, 67663 Kaiserslautern, Germany

⁸ Felix-Bloch-Institut für Festkörperphysik, Universität Leipzig, Linnestr. 5, D-04103 Leipzig, Germany

⁹ Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany

The NeXus data format [1] has been widely adopted across various scientific domains as a standardized way to store and exchange experimental data. In this presentation, we highlight how the use of the NeXus standard not only enables FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data exchange, but also serves as a bridge between raw experimental data and structured ontologies. By mapping complex experimental workflows and metadata into a standardized, ontology-compatible format, NeXus facilitates enhanced data integration, discovery, and reuse across disciplines.

We will demonstrate the power of this approach with examples from Optical Spectroscopy, Multi-dimensional Photoemission Spectroscopy, Electron Microscopy (EM), and Atom Probe Microscopy (APM) which are described by an overarching and consistent NeXus schema. We will show how the NOMAD platform [2] integrates NeXus and supports the entire experimental data lifecycle—from acquisition and annotation to sharing and reuse—thereby advancing a semantically rich and interoperable research data infrastructure.

Keywords: NeXus, ontology, Data schema

Funding

FAIRmat is funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft "DFG, German Research Foundation" – project 460197019.

References

- [1] M. Könnecke, F. A. Akeroyd, H. J. Bernstein, et al., "The nexus data format," *Journal of applied crystallography*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 301–305, 2015.
DOI:10.1107/S1600576714027575.
- [2] Nomad - materials science data managed and shared, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://nomad-lab.eu/>.